

Based on the World War II analogy described in Chapter 27 of Ares Le Mandat that deduces overall health to 2 opposing sides

Hydroxychloroquine, Vitamin D, blood thinners, and Remdesivir's effectiveness against COVID-19 have a common link

US President Trump has advocated for Hydroxychloroquine to be considered as an effective treatment for COVID-19. However, after a number of people have been reported to experience serious adverse side effects, the general consensus has -as a result- turned largely pessimistic about Hydroxychloroquine's effectiveness. The reason I considered the recommendation of a malaria drug as solid reasoning is based on my research in making sense of how overall health is divided mainly into two opposing sides. This is explained in Chapter 27 of Ares Le Mandat. The lineup of symptoms, vitamins, and minerals on one side can each fight against the symptoms, vitamins and minerals of the other side. My reasoning infers that because Vitamin E is designated to side one of health in Chapter 27, while flu is designated to side two, Vitamin E can easily be nominated as a candidate for treatment of anything flu-like(I infer COVID-19 as a flu-like illness). Because its hypothesized that anything on side one can fight against anything on side two, theoretically-as a result of that-any symptom, vitamin or mineral from side one is a contender to fight against any symptom, vitamin or mineral on side two. Judging from the way the components(symptom, vitamin or mineral) of each side is allocated- with high insulin on side one versus both flu and malaria on side two(see pg 533-534 of Chapter 27 of Ares Le Mandat)- Hydroxychloroquine with its high insulin/hypoglycemic side effect becomes a solid proposal in the fight against COVID-19. After reading about the fatal cases pertaining to Hydroxychloroquine use, I learned that the adverse effects mirrored strongly the adverse affects of extreme hypoglycemia and insulin overdose which both normally end in cardiac arrest. This is not the case for all reported treatments of COVID-19 with Hydroxychloroquine. Hydroxychloroquine has been found effective in some studies. Treatment with Hydroxychloroquine cut the death rate significantly in sick patients hospitalized with COVID-19 – and without heart-related side-effects, according to a new study published by Henry Ford Health System. <https://www.henryford.com/news/2020/07/hydro-treatment-study>

What Hydroxychloroquine does-in terms of how it applies to the Chapter 27 perspective-is draw from the high insulin component of side one and uses that to fight against the components of side two. Furthermore, it should not be surmised that this infers for a component of one side to be without problems should it be administered beyond what is necessary for treatment. This is happening with use of Hydroxychloroquine in some cases. A good analogy is drinking not just enough water just to satisfy one's thirst, but drinking too much to not only satisfy one's thirst but also go overboard and at the same time bring oneself to water intoxication. In this, one can understand such a scenario doesn't discount water altogether as an effective treatment for thirst. The key for any further research on Hydroxychloroquine would be in understanding the individual patient's initial level of insulin and administering based on that in order to circumvent the dangers of the hypoglycemia/high insulin overdose symptom of Hydroxychloroquine's adverse effects.

Moreover, what Chapter 27 of Ares Le Mandat does is show why there is more than one effective method to fight COVID-19 or any other disease.

Another example that affirms the side 1/side 2 layout of health described in Chapter 27 of Ares Le Mandat are the promising results that Vitamin D has shown in coronavirus research. Studies performed by Michael F. Holick--a professor of physiology, medicine and molecular medicine and biophysics at Boston University School of Medicine--found that COVID-19 patients over 40 who had sufficient Vitamin D levels were 51% less likely to die from the virus. It was also concluded that anyone who had sufficient levels of Vitamin D in his system had a reduced risk of catching the virus by 54%. Pages 533 and 534 of Chapter 27 of Ares Le Mandat has Vitamin D lined up on the same side of health as high insulin, which was the effect of Hydroxychloroquine protocols used to fight COVID-19. This further affirms the outlook of 2 opposing sides of health.

The success of blood thinners in treating COVID 19 also affirms the side 1/side 2 layout of health described in Chapter 27 of Ares Le Mandat. An observational study done by researchers at Mount Sinai

in New York found that hospitalized COVID-19 patients who took blood thinner prescriptions had a 50% reduced risk of death. They also checked autopsy records from COVID-19 patients at Mount Sinai and found that 11 of 26 patients had blood clots in the lungs, brain and heart that weren't detected in the hospital. <https://www.webmd.com/lung/news/20200827/blood-thinners-may-increase-covid-survival-rates> Scientists at Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute discovered the effectiveness of blood thinners in neutralizing the coronavirus. They found that the blood thinner heparin was effective in keeping the virus from infecting healthy cells. (<https://www.fiercebiotech.com/research/how-covid-19-could-be-crippled-by-age-old-blood-thinner>) The studies concerning blood thinners as an effective treatment justifies the Vitamin E proposal since it also has blood thinning properties. Pages 533 and 534 of Chapter 27 of Ares Le Mandat has blood thinning lined up on the same side of health as Vitamin D and high insulin.

On October 2, 2020, US President Donald Trump announced that he and the First Lady tested positive for Covid-19. He has been placed on a five-day course of treatment with remdesivir, an antiviral drug manufactured by drug maker company Gilead Sciences. One can gather from information regarding the side effects of remdesivir that remdesivir is also drawing from the side 1 of health explained in Chapter 27 of Ares Le Mandat, specifically from the gastroproblems that has been set as antagonistic to flu-like illnesses. The most common side effect discovered in patients treated for COVID-19 using remdesivir was nausea. This, according to the thesis outlined in Chapter 27 of Ares Le Mandat, makes remdesivir a solid proposal against the coronavirus. In a 600-patient analysis, published by the Journal of the American Medical Association, the study in moderately ill COVID-19 patients showed that 11 days after starting treatment--65% of the 10-day remdesivir patients, 70% of the 5-day patients and 60% of the standard care patients had left the hospital. "Side effects seen more frequently in the remdesivir groups included nausea, low blood potassium levels, and headache." (<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-health-coronavirus-remdesivir/gilead-fda-could-expand-remdesivir-use-despite-mixed-data-idUSKBN25H2CT>) Pages 533 and 534 of Chapter 27 of Ares Le Mandat has gastroproblems lined up on the same side of health as

blood thinning, Vitamin D, and high insulin.

This thesis of overall health being divided mainly into two opposing sides makes sense of how Hydroxychloroquine(high insulin effect), Vitamin D, blood thinners, and remdesivir(gastroproblem effect) are all effective against the coronavirus (COVID-19). This allows us to continue to build the list and allocate appropriately.

*-taken from pages 533 and 534 of Chapter 27 of Ares Le Mandat and modified with new additions in **bold***

Side one of health

High white blood cell

High blood insulin

High blood pressure

High HDL cholesterol

(good cholesterol)

Low LDL cholesterol

(bad cholesterol)

Cancer

Gastroproblems

VitaminE

Sickle Cell Anemia

Ebola-stage 2

Statins

Heart Attack

(heart disease)

Happiness(high

dopamine)

Vitamin D

Calcium

VitaminB12

Zinc

Alcohol

Blood thinning

Sodium

Hydroxychloroquine

Remdesivir

Elevated liver enzymes

Heparin

Side two of health

Low White blood cell

Low blood insulin

Low blood pressure

Low HDL cholesterol

(good cholesterol)

High LDL cholesterol

(bad cholesterol)

High Triglycerides

Flu symptoms

Vitamin A(beta carotene, sugar)

Malaria

Cardiogenic shock depression(low

dopamine)

Heart attack

(embolism)

Magnesium

VitaminC

VitaminK

Iron

Caffeine

Chemotherapy

Blood clot

Potassium

COVID-19

The hypothesis is that anything related to the causes and symptoms of side one can fight against anything related to the symptoms and causes of side two. Metaphorically, side one could be the allied powers and side two could be the axis powers

On the previous page, the aforementioned medical and health components that were factored into COVID-19 treatment possibilities during the year 2020 by various research institutions was added to the list that's displayed in chapter 27 of *Ares Le Mandat*: Hydroxychloroquine, Remdesivir, and Heparin. Other components like elevated liver enzyme count, sodium, potassium, and COVID-19 were also added to the list and allocated appropriately: elevated liver enzyme count & sodium on side one and potassium & COVID-19 on side 2. Making a decision on where to situate sodium and potassium was a complicated matter, but after making judgments based on factors mentioned in studies regarding flu medications and their effect on raising blood pressure along with factors described in the study of remdesivir treatments that link remdesivir to side effects of low potassium, I resolved to place sodium on side one with remdesivir as an ally in the fight against the components of side two. This automatically relegates potassium to side two. With potassium known to lower overall blood pressure and aid blood clotting mechanisms, it becomes justified to observe potassium as an ally of COVID-19 and a member of side two. The difficulty in making this decision came from observing studies by scientists at the National Cancer Institute's Center for Cancer Research that found that tumor cells rely on potassium in order to evade killer t cells. "In experiments with both mouse and human tumors, Restifo's team, including NCI surgical oncology research fellow Robert Eil (now at Oregon Health and Sciences University), found the fluid that fills the space between tumor cells can contain high levels of potassium, an ion that is usually concentrated inside cells." This extracellular fluid containing potassium was found to be immunosuppressive. This would imply that potassium is an ally of cancer and would thus contradict the thesis of potassium(side two) being on the opposing side of cancer(side one). However a study done by Jansson B. entitled "Potassium, sodium, and cancer: a review" affirmed that as potassium leaves the cells and sodium enters, the rate of cancer increases. The article states that "Patients with hyperkalemic diseases (Parkinson, Addison) have reduced cancer rates, and patients with hypokalemic diseases (alcoholism, obesity, stress) have increased cancer rates." This finding helps us infer that sodium is a carcinogenic agent and a contributor to cancer, and thus properly placed on side one on the lists presented in Chapter 27 of *Ares Le Mandat*. Please note hyperkalemic is abnormally elevated potassium while hypokalemic is abnormally reduced potassium. To resolve the contradiction between the studies, I could infer that potassium--as an antagonist to the carcinogenic agent

sodium--is seen by the killer t-cells as an ally(or as doing the same job) which would thus avert or delay the killer t-cell response. As long as potassium is present, it will always attempt to antagonize sodium even as its pushed out by increasing sodium levels in the cells and this in itself is an anti-tumor operation by the potassium. Human tumor cells contain significantly more sodium that it does potassium. A study of human tumors from 10 cancer patients with the cancers classified in three types: keratinizing, transitional cell, and hypernephroid carcinomaand compared with patients that have no malignant cancerous processes revealed that in all three types of cancer cells, the average intranuclear sodium content increased more than three-fold, while the potassium content decreased 32, 16, and 13%, respectively. (Source: Nagy IZ, Lustyik G, Nagy VZ, Zarándi B, Bertoni-Freddari C. Intracellular Na+:K+ ratios in human cancer cells as revealed by energy dispersive x-ray microanalysis. *J Cell Biol.* 1981;90(3):769-777. doi:10.1083/jcb.90.3.769)

Sources: Jansson B. Potassium, sodium, and cancer: a review. *J Environ Pathol Toxicol Oncol.* 1996;15(2-4):65-73. PMID: 9216787

<https://ccr.cancer.gov/news/article/high-levels-of-potassium-inside-tumors-suppress-immune-activity#:~:text=Potassium%20released%20from%20dead%20tumor,tumors%20evade%20the%20body's%20defenses.>